

D4.2 – Performance report on the Output Support Services

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Disclaimer

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Abbreviations, Terms, and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
HE	Horizon Europe
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
IG	Interest Group
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA Corpus	The body of work created by RDA over time
RDA-KB	RDA Knowledge Base
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SRIA	The Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TAB	RDA Technical Advisory Board
TG	Task Group
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WG	Working Group

Executive Summary

Research Data Alliance's (RDA) Working Groups (WGs) aim to solve specific research data related issues in a relatively short period of time. These groups are created by the RDA community, and rely on the voluntary contributions from the community to achieve its stated objectives. While this approach has been demonstrated to be successful in the last decade, certain areas have been identified where improvements can be made. The RDA TIGER project addresses some of these improvements [1].

RDA TIGER has established a suite of concrete services to support the Working and Interest Groups (WG) of the RDA. Work Package 4 in the TIGER project oversees the service for WG Output Support, including various output guidance services, and particularly the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB; previously referred to as the RDA Maintenance Platform (RDA-MP - see annex K for an overview of naming scheme changes). The objectives are to ensure high quality, usefulness, maintenance, and sustainability of the WG outputs.

This report provides an assessment of progress to date with the implementation of the work plan outlined in D4.1 [4], and highlights challenges and remedies for those challenges.

The report structure mirrors that of D4.1, since we assess progress with the implementation of the solutions and remedies identified in that report with respect to the main concerns, issues, and opportunities facing RDA working group and interest group activities.

Highlights

From left: The RDA Maintenance Facility Dashboard, Catalogue for Search and Discovery, and the RDA Annotation Tool (Browser Plug-In)

Figure 1: Applications developed by RDA TIGER

In summary, the highlights for the reporting period are the following:

1. The **RDA Knowledge Base** has been available since Plenary 21 as a beta version, and once feedback and suggestions for improvements have been processed (ongoing), it is aimed for public launch at Plenary 23.
2. The companion **RDA Annotator** tool (in previous project deliverables “Annotation Tool”) has been deployed for use by the RDA TIGER facilitation teams in support of working groups. The RDA Annotator underwent two separate development cycles during the course of the last year - an interim application was developed to assist with landscape analyses undertaken by RDA TIGER, and this was replaced with the current application in March 2023. A revised version will be published at the end of June 2024.
3. The **RDA Publisher** (in previous project deliverables “Deposit Pipeline”) is ready for use in a production environment, and while much of the application is not visible to end users with the exception of the **Resource Deposit Form**, it performs important tasks - preparing materials for automated deposit to Zenodo and to any future long-term repository.

4. The **RDA Graph** (in previous deliverables, occasionally referred to as the “Graph Database”) now contains a **fully curated snapshot of the RDA corpus**¹ (outputs and supplementary materials, extended by annotations), up to date until the end of March 2023. This curated version was not initially planned as part of the RDA TIGER WP4 task list, but it became clear that without such a well-curated corpus, the production releases of the RDA-KB and the Annotation Tool would not be useful.
5. Standardising, deduplicating, and linking **RDA Vocabularies and Registry Data** (see Annexure C) was completed, and necessary for deployment of a functioning RDA Graph Database (Annexure D).
6. A **draft metadata schema** for resource publication and annotation has been developed and implemented. This schema is fully aligned with the basic DataCite/ Zenodo schema, and extends it with RDA-specific elements and supporting vocabularies and registries.
7. **User guides, policies, and supporting materials (procedures)** are available in draft form at the present time, together with file format guidance (see Annexures).

Synergies and Exploitation

The resources and assets established by the RDA TIGER project are already of use in other Horizon Europe (HE) –funded environments, and there is potential for additional uses that have been proposed and/or identified. These co-creation and exploitation opportunities have several benefits, amongst other by improving the return on investment in code and infrastructure, and also ensuring better sustainability by involving a wider set of individuals and organisations in the improvement and extension of the open source code repositories underpinning the work. The fact that these outputs and services have already been implemented in other projects should also facilitate their roll-out within RDA TIGER.

Co-development and Exploitation Opportunities (Details - Section 5)

Component	In Progress				Planned
	RDA TIGER	FAIRCORE4EOSC , FAIR-IMPACT	OSTRails	Other	
RDA Discovery	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Configurable UI Forms	✓	✓		✓	
RDA Publisher	✓	✓		✓	✓
Annotation Tool	✓			✓	

Challenges

During the course of the last year, two main challenges emerged that required additional effort, caused a delay in completion of deliverables, and required re-allocation of resources.

1. While we anticipated initially to crowdsource the improvement of the RDA corpus (via RDA members), this task was performed internally by DANS and required a considerable effort. The

¹ 258 resources at the end of June 2024, excluding annotations.

RDA corpus grew organically over 10 years, with formal outputs and supplementary materials at first committed to the RDA website, and then to Zenodo. The structure and content of web pages describing outputs and supplementary materials changed over time, requiring manual data extraction in many cases, since automated methods could not always be used. Crowdsourcing as a final quality check for the corpus will still be done, and this is anticipated prior to the public launch of the RDA-KB and Annotation Tool at Plenary 23. The effort to create a credible database delayed the release of a beta version of the RDA-KB and the Graph Database by at least three months.

2. The new RDA website took longer than anticipated to be rolled out and quality assured. This had two impacts:
 - a. Pages that were available in the original website did not resolve (for example case statements, group pages, member pages...). These pages are often included as resource links in the RDA graph data. The situation is improving, but should the site not support all the links in the RDA Graph by end June, it is proposed that missing references be redirected to the legacy site (for which a snapshot is available with the assistance of the RDA Secretariat).
 - b. The engagement with the development team for the RDA website to implement vocabulary and registry services had to be postponed while they attended to the issues encountered with the roll-out. This engagement has now resumed (June 2024).

Outputs

The following is an overview and brief description of the outputs produced by WP4 to date. Further details regarding each of the outputs can be found mainly in section 3.

Outputs overview

Category	Output	Description
Policy and Procedures	Policy - Outputs	RDA will benefit from a policy in respect of output production and publication - dealing with aspects such as licensing and access, branding, ownership, attribution, and maintenance.
	Procedure: Workgroup Creation and Life Cycle	This exists to some degree, but must be reviewed in the light of additional support materials, guidelines, mechanisms, and tools required for the ' Output Definition Report ', and must align with policy ² .
	Procedure: Research Processes	Procedures for annotation and referencing of resources and publications in the course of the workgroup's activities.
	Procedure: Publication of Outputs	RDA Working Groups need to adopt a common procedure for publication of outputs and supplementary materials, based on the

² Clarity is needed from RDA on how this differs from Case Statements required from new groups. Needs to be differentiated clearly.

		RDA Knowledge Base.
	Procedure: Curation of RDA Collections	RDA collections in Zenodo [2],[3] need accession procedures that will ensure consistency of materials and resources in the collections.
	Procedure: Selection and Maintenance of Vocabulary	The process whereby RDA identifies vocabulary and how it is governed and maintained must be documented.
Standards and Benchmarks	Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies	RDA needs to use standard APIs and encodings for its own vocabularies. These need to extend to and allow the linking of external resources as intended in O1 and O3.
	Preferred Formats for Dissemination and Preservation	These are needed to maximise utility for the community and to ensure long-term preservation.
	Annotation Standards and Schema	RDA will define a number of standard schemas: metadata, rating, and landscape context are examples.
	Minimum Metadata Schema	These have to be differentiated for different output and resource types, while satisfying repository and RDA requirements.
Systems and Tool Solutions	RDA Knowledge Base	The RDA Knowledge Base plays a central role in support of WGs and associated RDA activities: publication, annotation, discovery, and preservation.
	RDA Annotator	Integration with annotation platforms such as OKRG and hypothes.is will broaden the scope of end users and extend the RDA graph/ knowledge base.
	Helpdesk	The Helpdesk assists working groups and other RDA members to request assistance with tools, software, templates, or any other solution element
Guidance and Support Solutions	Guidelines: Workgroup Establishment	Description of life cycle, which solution elements are available for and should be used in each step of the life cycle, and how to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate the Output Definition Report; • Create outputs and support materials that are publication and machine-ready. • Annotate and reference individual elements of outputs in a reusable way.
	Guidelines: Maximising Workgroup Effort	Includes landscape analysis support, annotation best practices, structuring of outputs and supplementary materials, making effort reusable - overlaps with the previous, but adds guidelines for annotation of web resources.
	Documenting Standards and Specifications	It is anticipated that standards and specifications will be occasional outputs from working groups, and to ensure that these are documented in a consistent and publishable way, a template with

		attendant guidance will be developed for this aspect. WP4 will endeavour to make use of EU-funded support services for this ³ .
	Informal Contributions to the 'RDA Graph'	It is possible and desirable for individual RDA members to annotate, rate, and comment materials referenced and produced by RDA. To assist with this, a guidance document will be developed.

³ <https://www.hsbooster.eu/>

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Table Legend

Throughout this report, tables are colour-coded with progress indicators, as below.

Excluded/ Not Achievable This task or output will not be achieved or has been removed from scope	Not Started Not started as planned, or still to be done.	Challenges/ Next Steps Challenges faced, and steps to mitigate, or next steps in multi-step implementation	Progress Implemented and/ or available
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1. Progress with Solutions and Remedies for Main Concerns

Research Data Alliance’s (RDA) Working Groups (WGs) aim to solve a specific research data related issue in a relatively short period of time. In practice, these groups are created by the RDA community, and rely on the voluntary contributions from the community to achieve its stated objectives. While this approach has been demonstrated to be successful in the last decade, certain areas have been identified where improvements can be made. The RDA TIGER project addresses some of these improvements [1].

Figure 2. Work Package structuring and activities in RDA TIGER [WP4]

Work Package 4 in the TIGER project oversees the service for WG Output Support, particularly the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB), and various output guidance services. The objectives are to ensure high quality, usefulness, maintenance and sustainability of the WG outputs. The WP aims to achieve this by contributing to and establishing the following:

- O1: Improvements to Output Definition;
- O3: Guidance for Policy Outputs;
- O4: Guidance for Standardisation;
- O5: Output Sustainability and Maintenance.

As an unspoken but necessary outcome one could state that the WP aims to make RDA outputs and associated resources FAIR.

1.1 Progress with Remedies for Identified Focus Areas

Work Package 4 in the RDA TIGER project developed a portfolio and approach to its support activities and infrastructure in a previous deliverable (D4.1 - Description of Output Support Services and Knowledge Base [4]). In D4.1, a number of broad issues, problems, desirable outcomes, and design considerations associated with RDA management of its corpus, and of RDA Working Groups that WP4 should focus on was identified. In this section, we report on progress and challenges, if any, in addressing these concerns and the remedies that were proposed in D4.1.

1.1.1 Curation-Related

Table 1. Curation-Related Focus Areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.1.1	Inconsistent Metadata	Over time, the publication of RDA outputs and supporting materials have been subject to change, and as a result, not all outputs and supplementary materials have similar metadata or a consistent curation process applied to them.	<p>Progress: A consistent metadata schema, aligned with Zenodo/ DataCite schema, but also extended to accommodate RDA-specific vocabularies has been defined, and implemented in the RDA-KB and the RDA Graph.</p>
1.1.1.2	Generalised Metadata	RDA outputs have been published to Zenodo for about 6 years now, and in such cases the minimum metadata associated with Zenodo/ DataCite publications are required. This metadata is generalised, and unless the depositor adds appropriate (and unmanaged) tags, RDA-specific elements are not accommodated in metadata.	<p>Progress: All legacy outputs have been processed and provided with missing metadata where appropriate.</p> <p>Next Steps: The process to do this is still manual, and will be automated once it is possible to integrate the RDA-KB more closely with the new RDA Website.</p>
1.1.1.3	Multiple repositories	RDA has used multiple repositories for both outputs and other supplementary materials over time. Zenodo contains a comprehensive collection of outputs, but it is not guaranteed to be complete. Zenodo also contains a partial collection of presentations, supplementary materials, reports, and other resources related to RDA, but so does the repository folders in the RDA website.	<p>Progress: All new deposits of outputs and supplementary materials will go to Zenodo, and all legacy resources - whether in RDA website, Zenodo, or elsewhere in the web has now been curated and included into one searchable catalogue.</p> <p>Next Steps: Automation of curation tasks. This is</p>

		Many supplementary materials, work in progress, and resources are stored in shared online repositories such as Google Drive, and are not archived under RDA control or curated by RDA.	under discussion with the RDA Secretariat.
1.1.1.4	Collection Management	The RDA has established two collections in Zenodo, one for formal outputs, and one for supplementary materials. Both these collections appear somewhat variable in terms of content despite a moderation requirement for deposits to the collections. The formal outputs collection, for example, contains non-outputs in the narrow sense of the word (i.e. not RDA-endorsed recommendations).	Progress: All legacy deposits in Zenodo have now been correctly classified as one of a number of resource types, correcting past mistakes.
			Next Steps: Curation tasks to be standardised at the RDA Secretariat, and processes documented as standard procedures. This is under discussion with the RDA Secretariat.
1.1.1.5	Long-Term Preservation	Outputs that are maintained and made available from the RDA website have very limited preservation certainty, and those published in Zenodo are likely to be preserved but Zenodo does not explicitly provide a long-term preservation service aligned with trustworthy repository criteria.	Progress: The RDA Publisher developed inter alia for RDA allows deposit of content to multiple targets, of which a suitable long-term repository can be one. Candidates include the DANS Vault (operational end 2024).
			Next Steps: Long-term copies of RDA deposits must still be tested and implemented.

1.1.2 Process-Related

Table 2. Process-Related Focus areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.2.1	Research Methodology	Recent improvements in annotation of web-based resources has implications for research methodology and management of references that can be included into working group practices.	Progress: An annotation tool is available for use by RDA members, annotating web content with RDA vocabulary.
			Next Steps: Dissemination and widespread use needs to be addressed - requesting a workshop session at RDA Plenary 23.

1.1.2.2	Landscape Analysis	Similarly, most Working Groups need to do some form of landscape analysis, and this is repeated without benefiting from similar analysis done within RDA or in associated initiatives in the landscape. (This aspect is addressed in detail in the work of RDA TIGER WP3).	<p>Progress: A sample of RDA TIGER landscape assessments have been imported into the catalogue (see Figure 3) and it is expected that future landscape analyses will be added to the corpus. This will now be done via engagement with the groups supported by RDA TIGER.</p>
1.1.2.3	Mobilisation and Re-use of Web Resources	During the course of the work of a Working Group, it is common to review a number of web-based resources and publications, and then analyse and synthesise the information, with working group and community input, into a set of recommendations, a model, or similar output. The effort expended in reviewing these input resources is often not re-usable except with some difficulty, given that at most the resources will be made available as references.	<p>Progress: Tool set (RDA Annotator and RDA Discovery) is available.</p> <p>Next Steps: Engaging RDA groups to disseminate tools and how best to apply them. Requesting a workshop session at RDA Plenary 23.</p>
1.1.2.4	Structuring of Recommendations	Recommendations, best practices, and guidelines are commonly reported in monolithic documents, making it difficult to find and re-use them across different documents or to aggregate a set of recommendations for a given topic.	<p>Not Started</p>
1.1.2.5	Publication Process	The publication process for RDA outputs and supplementary materials is not standardised, and has changed over time.	<p>Progress: Discussion on the need for standardisation has started with the RDA Secretariat, guidance document has been developed, and feedback received from the RDA Secretariat.</p> <p>Next Steps: Implementation across all groups. Requesting a workshop session at RDA Plenary 23.</p>
1.1.2.6	Dissemination Channels	RDA outputs are disseminated primarily via the RDA website, and there is limited possibility for third-party applications to harvest and use the corpus of RDA work in a different environment.	<p>Progress: Single catalogue has now been implemented.</p> <p>Challenges: Harvesting from ElasticSearch Catalogue to be tested, using standard APIs.</p>

			OAI-PMH endpoint to be considered.
1.1.2.7	Re-Use and Impact	Dissemination channel options, and partial publication of RDA outputs with persistent identifiers leads to limitations on re-use and gathering of metrics in respect of re-use.	Progress: All future resources published in Zenodo, with a DataCite DOI. DataCite provides citation metrics.

The screenshot shows the RDA Catalogue search interface. At the top, there are navigation links for 'DASHBOARD', 'SEARCH', and 'DEPOSIT', along with a 'LOG IN' button. A search bar contains the text 'Search documents'. Below the search bar, there are 'SORT BY' and 'LOAD SEARCH' buttons. The search results are displayed as '1 - 7 of 7 results'. The first result is 'ARDC Planet Research Data Commons', dated 'Sun Apr 14 2024'. It is described as 'National-scale data infrastructure for earth and environmental research and decision making'. The result includes metadata such as Language (English), Individuals (Rosie Hicks, Sheida Hadavi, Andrew Treloar, Richard Ferrers, Rhys Williams, Hamish ...), Rights (CC0 1.0, Open Access), Workflows (Web Resource), and Pathways (Data Infrastructures and Environments - International). Below the search results, there is a 'Year' bar chart showing a single bar for the year 7. The 'Active filters' section shows 'URI types Infrastructure' with 'CLEAR SEARCH' and 'SAVE SEARCH' buttons. The 'Individuals' section lists names and their counts, with a 'SHOW ALL (46)' link.

Figure 3: Examples of Landscape Analysis Annotations in the RDA Catalogue - in this case, 'Infrastructures' of interest to Working Groups supported by RDA TIGER.

1.1.3 Standards-Related

Table 3. Standards-Related Focus areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.3.1	Precision	The precision that can be expected of annotation increases significantly with standardisation of the vocabularies used for tagging.	Progress: This aspect has been fully implemented, and new vocabularies can easily be added via configuration of the RDA Annotation Tool.

			Significant effort went into creation of and curation of RDA vocabularies.
1.1.3.2	Metadata Standards	Standards for metadata applicable to different types of RDA outputs will improve interoperability and reusability.	Progress: This aspect has also been fully addressed via standardisation of RDA Metadata.
1.1.3.3	Templates, Branding, and Version Management	Standards for presentations, reports, recommendations, and the minimum content, branding, and versioning information for each of these will improve the image, reusability, and quality of the outputs.	Not Started

1.1.4 Complexity and Granularity

Table 4. Complexity and Granularity -Related Focus areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.4.1	Complex Landscape	<p>RDA working groups need to become aware of and understand their positioning in a landscape that is becoming ever more complex, with multiple initiatives and thrusts focused on the same issues and problems in the research data management ecosystem. It is important to identify:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • what has been previously done on a given subject and what should be considered in the Case Statements; • who is working on this subject area in the global Open Science (OS) landscape, including e.g., European Open Science Cloud projects, and; • who has the necessary expertise and interest to participate in these actions. 	<p>Progress: The data to find experts within the RDA membership on a given subject or domain has been curated and de-duplicated. Moreover, all available annotations, resources, organisations, and individuals can be found via search and discovery.</p>
			<p>Challenges/ Next Steps: Automated synchronisation of data on groups, members, and organisations with the new RDA website is ongoing but delayed due to website implementation issues. Detailed ‘views’ of organisations and members must still be implemented.</p>
1.1.4.2	Proliferation of Guidance and Outputs	There is a significant investment in the developed world in the creation and formulation of best practices, guidance, and recommendations in respect of a wide variety of topics of interest to the community. As yet, there is no real attempt to consolidate, standardise, and collate these resources to avoid duplication,	<p>Progress: Discussions are ongoing in the FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT projects to annotate their recommendations using the RDA-KB.</p>

		divergence, and maximise return from these investments, or to make them machine-readable and actionable.	Next Steps: Implementation towards the second half of 2024, early 2025. Possible extension to other HE-funded projects.
1.1.4.3	Buried Recommendations	Moreover, many of the recommendations, best practices, and guidance are reported within deliverables and outputs that are linked to project websites and structures, and as such are often not published in mainstream channels. Such reports seldom result in widely adopted recommendations or specifications governed by organisations such as ISO ⁴ , W3C, or IETF.	Not Started

1.1.5 Capacity

Table 5. Capacity-Related Focus areas

#	Focus	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.5.1	Voluntary Contributions	Working Groups are largely resourced via voluntary contributions from members, and in most cases only a few workgroup members contribute to the main body of work in the working group.	Not Started
1.1.5.2	Bias and Skewed Resources	Resources are sometimes available due to overlap and synergy with funded tasks and outcomes in which workgroup members participate. On the one hand, this contributes funded resources to the working group, but on the other hand, it results in disproportionate contributions from these sources - not always therefore a balanced view or broad consensus.	Not Started
1.1.5.3	Content Focus	Working Groups tend to focus on and have intentions to create content (a set of recommendations, a specification) and do not have capacity, experience, or incentives to look at other aspects of product	Not Started

⁴ ISO as a standards body may present other challenges: for example standards are not openly accessible by default.

		readiness: communication, adoption, dissemination, standards creation, and so on.	
1.1.5.4	Capital and Operating Expenditure	RDA receives most of its 'capital expenditure' for free, by way of voluntary contributions of members (many of whom are funded indirectly via grants or their institutions to participate). It is not feasible to rely on voluntary maintenance of RDA assets (outputs, especially) via the same mechanism: grants often do not focus on these activities, and maintenance cannot be left to ad-hoc arrangements.	Not Started

1.1.6 Objectives

Table 6. Objectives-Related Focus areas

#	Objective	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.1.6.1	Improved Quality	There is a need to make sure that all WG outputs meet minimum quality standards, and that these improve over time. Minimum quality standards include metadata schema adherence, using templates, and following guidelines and procedures.	Not Started
			Next Steps: Templates and procedures as proposed in this report to be implemented
1.1.6.2	Improved Usefulness	Usefulness of outputs are dependent on the perspective of the end-user, and working groups are expected to align with identified needs and expectations of the community. At least some usability is a direct result of standardisation and presentation (e.g. machine-readability, findability).	Progress: To the extent that the usability objective can be served by technical means, the goal has been achieved.
			Next Steps: Dissemination of support available to RDA members
1.1.6.3	Proper Maintenance	Proper maintenance of RDA outputs after publication - in the short term and in respect of long-term preservation - is not addressed adequately in current working group obligations - essentially an optional aspect of RDA member activity.	Progress: Possibility of 'Worker Groups' was raised at P21, and well received.
			Challenges/ Next Steps: Arrange for a BoF at P23
1.1.6.4	Improved Sustainability	Sustainability of RDA outputs may have to be evaluated against emerging principles for open scholarly infrastructure, for example as	Not Started

		exemplified by POSI.	
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1.2 Working Group Workflow and Processes

The Landscape Analysis report [5] produced by RDA TIGER identifies the following high-level steps in the life cycle of a working group:

- **Preparation:** The project support actions include careful preparation of the Working Groups, such as planning their timeline, wide dissemination of their existence for wider participation, resource allocation, and landscape analysis of similar activities.
- **Facilitation:** During the active WG period, the [RDA TIGER project] provides facilitation services, including dedicated facilitator(s) to ensure that the work progresses appropriately, communication and analysis services (e.g. landscape monitoring), and several optional direct support actions, such as hiring consultancy for support tasks (e.g. surveys), providing travel grants for meeting participants, and even supporting minor but necessary development or research tasks related to WG work with small 3rd party grants.
- **Finalisation:** Towards the end of each Working Group’s life cycle, and after, the project supports different actions towards concretisation, exploitation, maintenance, and sustainability of the WG results.

Figure 4. Amended and Proposed Workflows for Working Group Operations. The figure has been updated with progress towards establishment of supporting technologies and its application.

From D4.1: “Historically, RDA Working Groups have generated outputs in a non-standardised way, and the scope, granularity, and composition of the outputs were largely left to the working group to decide. This has advantages, since being too prescriptive can lead to limitations on working group creativity, and standardisation places a burden on voluntary effort to ensure compliance. As a result, working group outputs have been diverse. Moreover, maintenance is currently also voluntary, and there is no certainty

that outputs will be maintained, or progress to wider adoption vis. standards authorities such as ISO, IETF, or W3C.”

Work Package 4 in RDA TIGER aims to address these deficiencies, at least in part, by creating solution elements that contribute to steps in the workflow, and below, we report on progress in this regard.

Table 7: Updated progress in respect of workflow support in RDA TIGER

#	Objective	Description	Progress and Challenges
1.2.1	Preparation	Standardisation of the way in which workgroups do their research to maximise its reusability, and upfront guidance in respect of structuring and standardisation of outputs and supplementary materials.	Not Started
			Next Steps: Templates and procedures are available, dissemination workshops to be conducted with TIGER-supported groups.
1.2.2	Service support for WGs	(Facilitation, communication, landscape analysis and direct support services): These aspects will not be addressed by WP4, but by other activities in RDA TIGER. Optional 3rd-party grants allocated to selected working groups may require guidance and support from WP4.	N/A
1.2.3	Finalisation	This step will require direct assistance and support from WP4, ensuring proper publication, structuring, annotation, and dissemination of outputs, web-based resources referenced or created by the working group, and relevant supplementary materials.	Not Started
			Challenges/ Next Steps: None of the groups supported by RDA TIGER are ready for this step yet - once they are, support will be provided. Preparatory workshops are planned.
1.2.4	Maintenance	The RDA TIGER project also has a finite existence, but structures and procedures for maintenance of RDA outputs need to be considered and established during the lifetime of the project.	Not Started
			Next Steps: Arrange for a BoF at Plenary 23 to discuss a maintenance group for RDA resources and vocabularies.
1.2.5	Adoption	Likewise, the RDA TIGER project does not have in scope to facilitate the adoption of outputs formally in standards organisations such as ISO or W3C, but the process to do so can be established, agreed with relevant	Progress: Contact has been made with HSBooster ⁵ . Awaiting an assessment from them with an aim to develop generic guidance.

⁵ <https://www.hsbooster.eu/about-0>

		standards organisations, and included into WG guidance and procedures.	Next Steps: Develop generic guidance.
1.2.6	Standardisation of Legacy Outputs	RDA has historically produced outputs that are not standardised, and funding or collaboration opportunities need to be found to address this.	Progress: Two releases of improved and standardised resources (outputs, supplementary materials) have been made to date. No need for funding.
			Challenges/ Next Steps: Automated synchronisation with RDA website, agreement with Secretariat on curation process
1.2.7	Crowdsourcing	It will be possible for any interested party to contribute to the annotation effort, and initially, RDA members and participating institutions provide a starting point.	Progress: Technical infrastructure and support documentation is in place to accommodate this aspect within RDA.
			Next Steps: Arrange a dissemination event at P23.
1.2.8	EOSC Focus	This will require engagement with current EOSC projects and initiatives to maximise the standardisation of their future outputs.	Progress: Technical infrastructure is in place to accommodate this aspect, and the project is ready to engage HE projects and EOSC task forces in this regard.
			Challenges/ Next Steps: Arrange a dissemination event for HE projects/ Task Forces. Actively work in FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT to annotate recommendations.

1.3 Discussion on Cross-Cutting Challenges

Implementation of the support infrastructure envisaged in D4.1 was delayed due to 2 cross-cutting challenges:

1. **Data clean-up, deduplication, and linking:** creation of a definitive resource catalogue for RDA, based on agreed links to registers of members, organisations, and to controlled vocabularies proved to be much more difficult than anticipated, and the process took approximately 6 months longer than planned. DANS employed two data assistants during the first half of 2024 to help expedite the often manual and time-consuming task of improving data quality. The significant

improvement in quality and consistency of RDA resources should be maintained properly in future.

2. **Implementation of the new RDA website** took much longer than anticipated - and hence integration between the new website and the RDA-KB had to be postponed. That process has just been re-initiated (June 2024). The main impact is the continued need for manual synchronisation of data between the website and the RDA-KB, which is costly and may introduce errors.

We make some recommendations later based on lessons learned, but in the interim measures to improve the situation are underway.

2. Alignment with Work In Progress

Table 8: Status of alignment with work in progress

#	Objective	Description	Progress and Challenges
2.1.1	Landscape Service	The Landscape Service consists of two major components: the development and maintenance of the database containing landscape analyses, and the delivery of the actual landscape analyses to the WGs.	Progress: Landscape Analysis items have now been included into the RDA catalogue, and in future, can be updated via the RDA Annotation Plug-In.
			Next Steps: Gain momentum in use and scope of annotations - in RDA TIGER and supported groups.
2.1.2	RDA Knowledge Base	RDA TIGER will make use of and further refine the RDA Knowledge Base.	Progress: Implemented and ongoing
2.1.2.1	Provision of a Helpdesk and Service Level Support	Assisting users with queries, problems, issues, and suggestions for improvement, measured against a service-level agreement in terms of response and resolution time.	Progress: Implemented and ongoing
2.1.2.2	Issue and Request Resolution	Providing functional controller and developer support for resolution of technical system issues, resolving non-technical issues with assistance and contribution from RDA Secretariat staff.	Progress This is possible via the helpdesk, or via email (most suggestions for improvement from the TIGER users have been received via email). These issues are prioritised and implemented as they are registered.
2.1.2.3	Limited New Functionality Development	A prioritised list of new feature requests to be maintained from the ticket system, together with estimates of time and effort, system impact. If maintenance time is not taken up by issue resolution, the team can implement new features;	Progress This process is underway. See Annexure H for a summary list of issues attended to up to end June 2024.
2.1.2.4	Technical Workshops at RDA Events	Provision of one or more workshops peripheral to RDA events (plenaries) to coach and support system users.	Next Steps Planned for P23, after piloting with TIGER-supported groups prior to the plenary.
2.2.1	Basic Infrastructure	The RDA Knowledge Base provides a basic set of tools and infrastructure.	Progress Implemented and available - Annexure A.

2.2.2	Landscape Extension	This can and will be extended to accommodate the needs of RDA TIGER for landscape-related links.	Progress Implemented and available - Annexure B.
2.2.3	Object Extension	... extended within RDA to accommodate other digital objects that need to be managed	Not Started In scope: catalogue is able to provide details on members and organisations, in addition to resources.
2.2.4	Casting the net wider	Standardising the annotation and availability of domain knowledge about research data and code infrastructure and its management in a formal 'Body of Knowledge'	Not Started In scope: engaging HE projects and EOSC Task Forces to contribute. Specifically engage FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC.
2.3	Graph Database	"The work to establish vocabularies and graph infrastructure for use by WP4, based on 2.1 above, is well advanced and a first release can be expected at the end of June 2023."	Not Started A graph database was initiated and tested using Neo4j technology, but this has proven difficult to use initially for development. DANS is investigating a hybrid solution (relational database catalogue, made available via SKG-IF ⁶ compliant APIs.)

⁶ [SKG-IF](#) - Scientific Knowledge Graphs - Information Framework is defining APIs for exchange between knowledge graphs.

3. Status: Scope and Nature of Planned Solutions

The following tables lists the proposed solutions and tools that were planned for use in WP4 to support RDA Working Groups, and outlined in D4.1. In the table, the solutions are described, and current status is assessed in terms of progress and challenges/ next steps (if any).

3.1 Policy and Procedures

Table 9. Policy and Procedures Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.1.1	Policy - Outputs	RDA will benefit from a policy in respect of output production and publication - dealing with aspects such as licensing and access, branding, ownership, attribution, and maintenance.	Progress: Recommended policy amendments are shown in Annexure D.
			Next Steps: Engage Secretariat for adoption.
3.1.2	Procedure: Workgroup Creation and Life Cycle	This exists to some degree, but must be reviewed in the light of additional support materials, guidelines, mechanisms, and tools required for the ‘ Output Definition Report ’, and must align with policy ⁷ .	Progress: Recommended process amendments are shown in Annexure E.
			Next Steps: Engage Secretariat for adoption.
3.1.3	Procedure: Research Processes	Procedures for annotation and referencing of resources and publications in the course of the workgroup’s activities.	Progress: Recommended process amendments are shown in Annexure E.
			Next Steps: Engage Secretariat for adoption.
3.1.4	Procedure: Publication of Outputs	RDA Working Groups need to adopt a common procedure for publication of outputs and supplementary materials, based on the RDA Knowledge Base.	Progress: Recommended process amendments are shown in Annexure E.
			Next Steps: Engage Secretariat for adoption.
3.1.5	Procedure: Curation of RDA Collections	RDA collections in Zenodo [2],[3] need accession procedures that will ensure consistency of materials and resources in the collections.	Progress: Recommended process amendments are shown in Annexure E.
			Next Steps: Engage Secretariat for adoption.

⁷ Clarity is needed from RDA on how this differs from Case Statements required from new groups. Needs to be differentiated clearly.

3.1.6	Procedure: Selection and Maintenance of Vocabulary	The process whereby RDA identifies vocabulary and how it is governed and maintained must be documented.	Progress: Recommended sources of truth are documented in Annexure C.
			Next Steps: Engage Secretariat for adoption.

3.2 Standards and Benchmarks

Table 10. Standards and Benchmarks Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.2.1	Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies	RDA needs to use standard APIs and encodings for its own vocabularies. These need to extend to and allow the linking of external resources as intended in O1 and O3.	Progress: Preliminary, curated lists are available.
			Next Steps: Engage Secretariat for definition of a curation process - potentially involving a new permanent WG in RDA (Annexure J).
3.2.2	Preferred Formats for Dissemination and Preservation	These are needed to maximise utility for the community and to ensure long-term preservation.	Progress: Refer to Annexure G.
			Next Steps: A curation mechanism is required - potentially involving a new permanent WG in RDA.
3.2.3	Annotation Standards and Schema	RDA will define a number of standard schemas: metadata, rating, and landscape context are examples.	Progress: A basic annotation schema has been defined - see Annexure F.
			Next Steps: Schema for ratings or adoption, organisations, and individuals can be considered.
3.2.4	Minimum Metadata Schema	These have to be differentiated for different output and resource types, while satisfying repository and RDA requirements.	Progress: Metadata schema has been defined - See Annexure F.
			Next Steps: Confirmation by Secretariat, and governance by permanent WG in RDA (Annexure J).
3.2.5	Templates for Output Reports, Recommendations	A number of standardised templates are needed for typical RDA outputs and supporting	Not Started

	, Standards and Specifications	materials. One objective is to simplify annotation and machine-readability.	Next Steps: Engage with HSBooster ⁸ to obtain guidelines, best practices, and recommendations.
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3.3 Systems and Tools

Table 11. Systems and Tool Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.3.1	RDA Knowledge Base	The RDA Knowledge Base plays a central role in support of WGs and associated RDA activities: publication, annotation, discovery, and preservation.	Progress: Available.
			Next Steps: Start implementation via RDA TIGER supported WGs, public release at P23.
3.3.2	Reference Managers	Integration between mainstream Reference Managers and the RDA MP will benefit end-users.	Not Started
			Next Steps: Wait to determine needs.
3.3.3	Annotation Platforms	Integration with annotation platforms such as OKRG and hypothes.is will broaden the scope of end users and extend the RDA graph/ knowledge base.	Progress: Available.
			Next Steps: Start implementation via RDA TIGER supported WGs and RDA Landscape Research, public release at P23.
3.3.4	Helpdesk	The Helpdesk assists working groups and other RDA members to request assistance with tools, software, templates, or any other solution element	Progress: Helpdesk available.
			Next Steps: Should not require training, but to be included into pre-P23 and P23 workshops.
3.3.5	Helpdesk Knowledge Base	The guidance and support materials (below) serve as an entry point to the policies, procedures, standards, tools, and best practices available to working groups. These are made available as HelpDesk knowledge base articles, in addition to being published and annotated.	Not Started
			Next Steps: Deploy once a technical decision has been made.

⁸ <https://www.hsbooster.eu/about-0>

3.3.6	The 'RDA Graph' (See Annexure D)	The need to accommodate a wider set of entities, concepts, and relations emanating from RDA within its landscape and ecosystem has to be accommodated: largely by providing access to additional schema, vocabularies and registries as a basis for annotation.	Progress: A first (test) implementation was deployed to Neo4j, and a decision was taken to work without a graph-only implementation until a stable operational system is in place.
			Next Steps: Take a technical decision after P23, and implement.

3.4 Guidance and Support

Table 12. Guidance and Support Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.4.1	Guidelines: Workgroup Establishment	Description of life cycle, which solution elements are available for and should be used in each step of the life cycle, and how to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate the Output Definition Report; • Create outputs and support materials that are publication and machine-ready. • Annotate and reference individual elements of outputs in a reusable way. 	Progress: Guidance schema is presented in Annexure E.
			Next Steps: Confirmation and refinements from Secretariat, and dissemination after that to the broader RDA membership.
3.4.2	Guidelines: Maximising Workgroup Effort	Includes landscape analysis support, annotation best practices, structuring of outputs and supplementary materials, making effort reusable - overlaps with the previous, but adds guidelines for annotation of web resources.	Progress: Documented guidelines in Annexure E.
			Next Steps: Confirmation and refinements from Secretariat, and dissemination after that to the broader RDA membership.
3.4.3	Documenting Standards and Specifications	It is anticipated that standards and specifications will be occasional outputs from working groups, and to ensure that these are documented in a consistent and publishable way, a template with attendant guidance will be developed for this aspect. WP4 will endeavour to make use of EU-funded support services for	Progress Preliminary recommendations are included in Annexure, but will be adjusted based on guidance from HSBooster.
			Next Steps: Await feedback and guidance from HSBooster.

		this ⁹ .	
3.4.4	Standards Authority Adoption Guidelines	Further support of the process of creating and disseminating standards and specifications: guidance will be developed, in consultation with e.g. ISO and W3C to guide working groups on processes to formally adopt their work. Will also make use of EU-funded support services where applicable ⁴ .	<p>Not Started</p> <p>Next Steps: Await feedback and guidance from HSBooster.</p>
3.4.5	Informal Contributions to the 'RDA Graph'	It is possible and desirable for individual RDA members to annotate, rate, and comment materials referenced and produced by RDA. To assist with this, a guidance document will be developed.	<p>Progress: Annotation is possible at the present time. Guidance is presented in Annexure E.</p> <p>Next Steps: Implement additional schema (ratings, ...) as agreed with the user community.</p>

3.5 Capacity Enhancement, Training, and Service Assistance

Table 13. Capacity Solutions

#	Solution	Description	Progress and Challenges
3.5.1	Workshops: Workgroup Output Support	Training materials and plenary-aligned workshops to highlight and introduce the support mechanisms developed by RDA TIGER.	<p>Not Started</p> <p>Next Steps: Training materials are available. Workshops to be arranged starting in Q3 2024, with an open event at P23.</p>
3.5.2	Service Assistance: Curation	Curation activities for Working Groups to publish their efforts and outputs in the recommended way. Included into plenary workshops.	<p>Not Started</p> <p>Next Steps: To start in Q3 2024 with WGs that are ready to publish resources, with an open event at P23.</p>
3.5.3	Alignment with other TIGER initiatives	The solution elements should be included into and align with relevant TIGER deliverables - see 4.2 below.	Not reported here - see section 4.2

⁹ <https://www.hsbooster.eu/>

4. Implementation

4.1 Progress with implementation

The work in RDA TIGER WP4 fits into a wider context, with alignment of milestones and deliverables to RDA Plenary events, funding opportunities, and ongoing EU-funded projects within the EOOSC initiative. These interrelated opportunities all, in principle, contribute to the establishment of an RDA body of knowledge, as described in D4.1. Figure 4 outlines this process.

Figure 4: Overview of Opportunities to complete the Body of Knowledge - updated from D4.1

Bear in mind that there are several dependencies not within control of the RDA TIGER project - for example the willingness and level of uptake of available tools and infrastructure by Horizon Europe projects and EOOSC Association Task Forces¹⁰, or the availability of and synchronisation with the new RDA website.

4.2 Timelines and Dependencies - Planned

Table 14. Plenary-aligned objectives

Plenary	Main Objectives	Status
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¹⁰ The EOOSC Association Task Forces completed their first charters at the end of 2023, and there has been a 6-month hiatus during reformulation of charters for a follow-up - this is now under way.

P21	Disseminate procedures in respect of Research Processes and Curation of RDA Collections	<p>Progress: Annexure E reports on the documented procedures.</p> <p>Next Steps: Dissemination at P23</p>
	Standardise Preferred Formats for Dissemination and Preservation, and Minimum Metadata Schema	<p>Progress: Annexure G reports on the preferred formats guidance and supporting tools.</p> <p>Next Steps: Possible implementation of conversion service to support guidance.</p>
	Implement the RDA Knowledge Base, Helpdesk, and Helpdesk Knowledge Base	<p>Progress: A first release of the RDA-KB was published as a beta version with sample data (release 1) in July 2023, and demonstrated with real data (release 2) at the P21 in Salzburg.</p>
	Publish guidelines for Workgroup Establishment	<p>Progress: Draft guidelines are available, not yet published.</p> <p>Next Steps: Deploy in the new RDA website, if agreed by the Secretariat. See Annexure E.</p>
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	<p>Not Started Added to tasks for pre-P23 implementation.</p>
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	<p>Progress: This process is currently undertaken manually by a curation team at DANS, and to date three releases of manually curated RDA resources have been made.</p> <p>Next Steps: A fourth manually curated release is foreseen (August 2024) before synchronisation with the new RDA website is in place.</p>
P22	Implement the Annotation Platform	<p>Progress: This has been deployed as a beta version, and one round of formal feedback from TIGER users has been implemented. Prior to this release, an interim annotation tool was released to TIGER users to assist with landscape analysis. See Annexure B.</p> <p>Next Steps: Small improvements are underway, a new release will be made available well before P23.</p>
	Publish guidelines for Maximising	<p>Progress:</p>

	Workgroup Effort	Draft guidelines are available, not yet published. See Annexure E.
		Next Steps: Deploy in the new RDA website, if agreed by the Secretariat.
	Operationalise and explain Informal Contributions to the 'RDA Graph'	Not Started Added to tasks for P23 workshop.
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	Not Started Added to tasks for pre-P23 implementation.
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	Progress: Curation team is in place, and support materials and infrastructure are ready to offer a service.
		Next Steps: Support the working groups in scope for RDA TIGER from now on, and extend to the RDA community by Plenary 23.

4.2 Timelines and Dependencies - Revised

Due to a delay of approximately 6 months in having a production-ready dataset integrated with the new RDA website, some of the Plenary-related activities have to be rescheduled. This revised activity and implementation plan is summarised below.

Table 15: Revised Implementation Plan

Plenary	Main Objectives	Planning
Pre-P23	Disseminate procedures in respect of Research Processes and Curation of RDA Collections	Arrange a series of workshops with TIGER-supported working groups to test and refine procedures in time for dissemination at P23
P23	Disseminate procedures for Workgroup Creation and Life Cycle, and for Selection and Maintenance of Vocabulary	These can all be accommodated in a workshop aimed at RDA members in general, and specifically focusing on group chairs.
	Disseminate procedures in respect of Research Processes and Curation of RDA Collections	
	Publish and introduce community maintenance of Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies, as well as Annotation Standards and Schema	
	Release an updated version of the RDA Knowledge Base, and the Helpdesk Knowledge Base	Work to do this is under way as routine maintenance, and with a specific set of

		new functionalities in mind: 1. Semantic Search 2. Graph database API 3. Support for non-output objects - individuals, organisations.
	Publish guidelines on Documenting Standards and Specifications, and on Standards Authority Adoption	These guidelines depend on the engagement with HSBooster, but the process is underway.
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	Include into the P23 Workshop
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	Ongoing from P23 onwards
P24	Publish and disseminate an RDA Policy on Output and an updated Minimum Metadata Schema	Not planned yet.
	Release integration of Reference Managers and external Annotation Platforms	
	Conduct one or more workshops to introduce the above to Working Groups	
	Service assistance with curation of RDA materials	

5. Exploitation Opportunities

The resources and assets established by the RDA TIGER project are already of use in other HE-funded environments, and there is potential for additional uses that have been proposed and/ or identified. These co-creation and exploitation opportunities have several benefits, amongst other by improving the return on investment in code and infrastructure, and also ensuring better sustainability by involving a wider set of individuals and organisations in the improvement and extension of the open source code repositories underpinning the work.

Table 16: Co-development and Exploitation Opportunities

Component	In Progress				Planned
	RDA TIGER	FC4E/ F-I	OSTRails	Other	
Search and Discovery	#1	#5	#6	#7	#8
Configurable UI Forms	#2	#5		#7	
RDA Publisher	#3	#5		#7	#9
Annotation Tool	#4			37	

#: Opportunities as listed below.

The following list explains these opportunities in more detail:

1. The Search and discovery mechanism is used in RDA TIGER for multiple dashboard and catalogue views - resources (including annotations), individuals, and organisations.
2. Configurable UI Forms are used in RDA TIGER to compose forms for metadata capture on deposit and submission to Zenodo, and for capturing the content of an annotation. In RDA TIGER, these forms can also be reconfigured to collect ratings of resources, or for any other annotation schema.
3. The RDA Publisher is used to prepare metadata and content for submission to Zenodo, and in time to a long-term preservation facility.
4. The Annotation Tool is used in RDA TIGER to annotate the RDA Graph with resources useful to RDA groups - focusing initially on landscape analysis, but extending in future to any reusable research conducted by RDA groups.
5. FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT make use of the same components, except for the Annotation Tool, in two streams of work.
 - a. The [Compliance Assessment Toolkit](#) (WP2) in FAIRCORE4EOSC uses the Search and Discovery component in two additional roles: to provide a catalogue of PID services compliant with EOSC PID Policy, and to provide a catalogue of the characteristics and features of PID services for purposes of selection by end users.
 - b. The Configurable UI Form and RDA Publisher is used by FAIRCORE4EOSC (WP6) to demonstrate the dual deposit of research outputs to multiple target repositories - based on a common metadata schema, datasets are deposited to Dataverse, and code is deposited to Software Heritage, with mutual updates of linked identifiers.
6. The OSTRails project will likely use the Search and Discovery component to find tests, metrics, criteria, and FAIR-compliant objects in the FAIR Assessment space, with extension to accommodate domain-specific nuances and refinements (for example as in FAIR Implementation Profiles).
7. Several other projects make use of the same components (again with the exception of the Annotation Tool).
 - a. The nationally funded OH-SMART project in the Netherlands makes use of the Configurable UI Form and the RDA Publisher, and were the original funders of these two components. It has since implemented many refinements that can in future be useful in a wider context - including pre-submission quality assurance (for example verifying file formats and converting them if required). It also supports metadata transformation to suit the target repository, as needed, but the RDA TIGER case does not need this at the present time.
 - b. The RDA Publisher will be used for the first time in a semantic data transformation prior to deposit in a nationally funded project in the biodiversity field (Netherlands).
 - c. DANS has experimented with the Search and Discovery component for wider application, and we will be looking shortly at the incorporation of the Search and Discovery component and the Configurable UI Form into the new Dataverse architecture, opening up its maintenance and refinement to a large international open source community.
8. The Search and Discovery component has been introduced by DANS as a possible technology base for several EU funding call proposals - including use as an inventory tool for the desirable characteristics and features or trustworthy repositories and services, mechanisms to find and select tools, workflows, and value-added processing options for datasets, and a way to create a catalogue of best practices and recommendations in respect of data quality and reusability.

9. The RDA Publisher has not been explicitly included into new proposals to date, but services that can be utilised by the pipeline have: FAIR evaluation, licence evaluation and guidance, thumbnail creation, and similar are examples of these.

6. Recommendations and Next Steps

6.1 Next Steps

The period up to RDA Plenary 23 (November 2024) will require that TIGER WP4, in collaboration with WP3 and WP5, to achieve the following objectives:

1. Obtain user feedback on the usability and utility of the RDA-KB, the Annotation Tool, the RDA Graph, and the associated support materials and services through a first engagement with those groups being directly supported by the RDA TIGER project. The feedback needs to be received and acted on in time for the RDA Plenary 23 in November 2024, so that the public launch of the services and workshops to support the launch can be scheduled during the plenary.
2. Complete maximal integration with the new RDA website - including not only aspects of vocabulary and registry synchronisation, but also authentication and identification of members, and the integration of search and discovery and resource publication workflows into the new website.
3. Engagement with the RDA Secretariat to validate and adopt draft procedures, policy inputs, and other supporting documentation.
4. Establishment of a permanent ‘Worker Group’ in RDA to govern and manage RDA information assets (outputs, supplementary materials, and other web-based resources).

In parallel, there will be some improvements to the RDA-KB, the Annotation Tool, and the RDA Graph during this time:

1. Linking external Scientific Knowledge Graphs (e.g. the OpenAIRE Graph) to the RDA Graph for the purposes of semantically improved search and discovery;
2. Publication of APIs for the RDA Graph that supports the framework in development within the RDA Working Group on Scientific Knowledge Graphs ([SKG-IF](#)) and the [FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) project;
3. Extending the detailed views available within the RDA-KB to include, *inter alia*, RDA Members and organisations linked to RDA in one way or another.

6.2 Recommendations

1. Discuss the possibility of deploying the RDA Annotation Tool as a formal plug-in for Google Chrome.
2. Formal arrangements need to be made with the RDA Secretariat to integrate the TIGER infrastructure (RDA-KB, Annotation Tool) with the new RDA Website in respect of authentication, search and discovery, and outputs publication.
3. The activities in respect of publication of RDA outputs as formal standards has a dependency on an EU-funded project (HSBooster¹¹) as a first option. Contact has been initiated but responses

¹¹ <https://www.hsbooster.eu/about-0>

have been very slow - a formal engagement is required to convey the importance of the contribution that they can make to RDA.

References

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- [4] TIGER D4.1 – Description of Output Support Services and Maintenance Platform (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096631>
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- [8] RDA TIGER (2024): Publication of RDA Resources, https://docs.google.com/document/d/1DCSbyGfyprfpH9GORTbMwb15vEOZ7Yw6ZLEigsMtPSs/edit?usp=drive_link

Annexures

A: Maintenance Platform

Source Code: <https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/dans-frontend-framework>

RDA-specific code and configuration:

<https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/dans-frontend-framework/tree/main/apps/rda>

The RDA-KB is a composite application that uses several components in the DANS Front-End Framework ('WebFrame'):

1. The Search and Discovery Application (which incorporates a Dashboard sub-component and a Catalogue View sub-component). The application currently works for ElasticSearch-based catalogues, but porting it to SOLR or other catalogues should be fairly simple.
2. A Configurable UI Form that is created based on a metadata schema, form component definition, and help/ tooltip/ completeness information. This form can be deployed for a wide variety of schemas, and can select, optionally pre-process, and verify files for deposit and upload.
3. An authentication and authorisation component that is integrated with federated identity management (at present supplied by SURF in the Netherlands - it allows authentication e.g. via ORCID and Google Accounts, as well as Edugain Accounts), linked to a Keycloak implementation as middleware to manage identities and tokens associated with an account. With a little bit of work, this facility can, for example, be used to log in via ORCID, but store credentials for the RDA Website and Zenodo so that interactions with these services can be automated.
4. These components are embedded in a Web Framework that takes care of layout and branding configuration, navigation and menu settings, and footer configuration.
5. The DANS Frontend Framework is linked to the RDA Publisher application, which takes care of metadata and data preparation and transformation, asynchronous uploads for large files, and similar concerns. The RDA Publisher can be configured for multiple deposit targets - in the case of RDA, one might want to deposit copies of a resource to Zenodo, to a long-term preservation platform, and possibly the RDA website in one automated execution.

Technology choices and stack includes Javascript/ TypeScript, React, json and json-ld, KeyCloak, Python, and XSLT.

The following sections highlight the features of the RDA-KB.

A.1 Webframe and its Configuration

The webframe component provides aspects such as branding, navigation, and authentication, and this is configurable separately.

A configurable, flexible webframe is used to define and deploy applications

Dashboards can be configured to present any combination of facets, and can be presented as maps, charts, timelines, and searchable lists of text.

Any selection within a facet instantly updates all the other facets, allowing an interactive drill-down approach to finding resources.

Footers are also configurable and can be branded to suit the application

Figure A.1 Webframe Application Configured and Branded for RDA TIGER

The Webframe application can be deployed as a single application, but it is also possible to deploy individual components (dashboard, search and discovery, and deposit form) as stand-alone apps or embed it into any other TypeScript/ React application with some rework and adjustment.

A.2 Dashboard¹²

One or more Dashboard views can be configured and deployed, and each of these can support one of the following variations in terms of content:

¹² A demo-version of the dashboard can be accessed on: <https://rda.dansdemo.nl/>

1. The source of content can be based on a single ElasticSearch instance, but configured for multiple indices and facets. This supports the situation where more than one entity in a catalogue is of interest (e.g. web resources, individuals, organisations, RDA outputs and supplementary materials, and so on). The applicable facets and detailed views for each of these entities will be different.
2. Each dashboard can alternatively be wired to a separate ElasticSearch instance, but this is not likely to be used by RDA.

Figure A.2 Dashboard View in the Maintenance Platform - Detail

A.3 Search and Discovery

The Search and Discovery component is configured separately, based on the same indices and facets used for the Dashboard component. The Search and Discovery component provides the same features as typically found in similar applications, and these are highlighted in Figures A.3.1-A.3.4.

Entries in the catalogue are constrained by the current filter settings, and can be ordered based on any of the facets. Paging of large catalogue views is available.

The Search and Discovery Component

The Search and Discovery component is presented in a typical and very common layout - facets for filtering towards the right-hand, and instances of catalogue entries on the left.

Figure A.3.1 Layout of the Search and Discovery Component.

Figure A.3.2 Improved Support for Free-Text Search

Figure A.3.2 Facets Can Be Configured In a Number of Type-Related Presentations

Figure A.3.3 Filtering Text Facets

The ability to filter individual text-based facets based on a type-ahead search is an important feature for large lists - for example lists containing all RDA Members.

Figure A.3.4 Saving, Changing, and Clearing Filters

A.4 Authentication Component

The Authentication Component allows use of federated identity, largely aligned with the research and higher education services worldwide via Edugain¹³ in addition to popular identity providers such as Google and ORCID. At present, the configuration is limited, but many other providers can be added.

Figure A.4 Authentication Options

¹³ Edugain: <https://technical.edugain.org/status>

B: Annotation Plug-In

Annotation Tool: <https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/rawr>

B.1 Interim Version

An interim application was developed in Q4 2023 to assist with Landscape Analysis tasks in TIGER WP3. The use and deployment of this application is described [here](#) for the record, access will be granted on request.

B.2 Final Version

B.2.1 Installation

This application can be downloaded and installed as [described in the video](#). The description below summarises the process as well.

Step	Description
1	Ensure that the plug-in is downloaded, installed, and activated in your browser. To do so, one generally can open a settings page to manage plug-ins that have been downloaded and installed. These steps are described below.
2	<p>First download and expand the zip file containing the plug-in application, as shown below, and then extract the files to any suitable location on your local hard drive.</p>
3	After expansion, the application can also be moved to a convenient permanent location

	<p>on your local hard drive (not recommended to leave it in the download folder). Depending on the operating system, one can also specify a target for expansion of the zip file.</p>
<p>4</p>	<p>In the next step, we install the plug-in in our browser. For the moment, the instructions are meant for Chrome browsers, and depending on the need, more browsers types will be supported in future. The plug-in should also work in Brave.</p> <p>To add a browser plug-in (extension), go to the settings icon at the very top right of the browser window and click. The settings menu will open, and in there an entry for 'Extensions' can be found.</p>
<p>5</p>	<p>Click on 'Manage Extensions'. A page with currently available extensions is shown, and one can add extensions here as well.</p>

6	<p>For the RDA Plug-In, one will select an application from disk, and not search for it in Google Play¹⁴.</p> <p>IMPORTANT: To load extensions from disk, the ‘Developer Mode’ has to be enabled. Once the extension is deployed in Google Play, this step will not be needed.</p> <p>To enable, click the switch at the top right of the ‘Manage Extensions’ page:</p>
7	<p>To load the extension, click on the ‘Load Unpacked’ button at the top left, and select the location (folder) where the application has been extracted to (steps 2, 3).</p>

¹⁴ Once the Plug-In is ready for production use, we will deploy it to Google Play.

7 Once the Plug-In extension has been registered, it will show up in the list of extensions for the browser - clicking the button at the bottom right of the 'card' will enable it in the browser.

8 Once this is done, the extension can be used, but it is far simpler to pin it to the Browser Toolbar so that it is instantly available (top right of your Browser) - it will show as a small RDA icon :

9	<p>To pin the extension to the Toolbar, click the 'Details' button in the 'Manage Extensions' Page:</p>

B.2.2 Annotating Web Resources

RDA has developed an Annotation Plug-In (currently available for Chrome browsers) that simplifies additions to the RDA Knowledge Graph. The main applications of the Annotation Tool are:

1. Allowing RDA members to make their landscape analyses and research during group activities reusable in the context of RDA and beyond;
2. Allowing RDA members to annotate and comment RDA outputs and supplementary materials, thereby improving its value.

A separate user manual will be published based on the current guidelines¹⁵ for RDA TIGER members. After installation (B2.1), the tool can be used as described below.

Step	Description
1	Open a web page and highlight some text that you wish to annotate.
2	Invoke the RDA Annotation Tool by clicking the RDA Plug-In icon in the toolbar.

¹⁵ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TmGJGysVF-igjTNRit3t1L1pspaN7IagAkB2w01XViv/edit?usp=sharing>

4	<p>The user can then fill in details about the annotation.</p>
5	<p>Depending on selected vocabularies, the user can match vocabulary entries with the annotation - this creates linked open data references to the annotation in the RDA Graph</p>

	<p>Created At * 27/6/2024</p> <p>Pathways FAIR</p> <p>Gorc Attributes</p> <p>Working Groups</p> <p>Disciplines (Domains)</p> <p>SUBMIT</p> <p>Vocabularies all have 'type-ahead' behaviour - typing a phrase will match vocabulary entries that can then be selected</p> <p>Once can select more than one entry from each vocabulary</p> <p>Entries can be removed by clicking the [x] on any specific tag</p> <p>Pathways FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Adoption, Implementation, and Deployment X FAIR, CARE, TRUST - Principles X</p> <p>Gorc Elements ICT Infrastructure* X</p> <p>Gorc Attributes Community* Definition X</p> <p>Working Groups CURE-FAIR WG X FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG X</p>
6	<p>When ready, click 'Submit'. The annotation is written to the RDA Graph.</p>
	<p>Working Groups CURE-FAIR WG X FAIRsharing Registry: Connecting data policies, standards and databases RDA WG X</p> <p>Disciplines (Domains)</p> <p>SUBMIT</p> <p>Additional Information Select an RDA Scientific Discipline (Domain) from the list. You can start typing to filter the list.</p> <p>Explanations for each vocabulary list is available</p> <p>Submit the annotation to the RDA Graph</p>

C: Vocabularies and Registries

Proper maintenance and curation of RDA resources and digital assets depend strongly on the quality and extent of use of definitive vocabularies and registries, listed below. The working [latest version of this list](#) is maintained separately¹⁶. In addition to vocabulary commonly used by RDA, RDA-external assets that are of relevance to the RDA Community, such as the GORC Commons Model, were added."

Table C.1 Vocabularies and Registries Summary

#	List Item	Description	Best Possible Current Source	Best Possible Future Source	Maintained in New Website
1	Plenary	A list of plenaries, with a reference to the host city	Provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
2	Disciplines Also: Disciplines	The standard disciplines (scientific domains) for which RDA creates output	Provided by RDA Secretariat	Frascati classification	No
3	Event	Events supported and hosted by RDA	Sample provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
4	Event Types	Event types hosted by RDA	Confirmation provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
5	Working Groups	RDA Working Groups	Provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
6	Interest Groups	RDA Interest Groups	Provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes

¹⁶ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1NWXsxfC8Oq99Po1E2NollyTGe-4lGOcCw1LiFljnlcM/edit#gid=1069203209&range=A1>

7	Communities of Practice	Communities of Practice in RDA	Provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
8	BoF	Birds of a Feather Sessions	Sample provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
9	Institution	Institutions associated with RDA	Sample provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API, PID Reference	Yes
10	Institution Role	Roles of institutions within RDA	Confirmation provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
11	Individuals (Members)	List of members of RDA (qualified with ORCIDS, ... where available)	Provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API, PID Reference	Yes
12	Individual Role	Roles of individuals in the	Confirmation provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
13	Organisational Bodies	RDA organisational bodies	Confirmation provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
14	Principles	Sets of principles that guide and inform RDA work	Sample provided by DANS	EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit	No
15	Researchers	Researchers are a subset of the membership of RDA, there is an overlap between researchers and members	ORCID	ORCID	No
16	Repositories	Repositories are listed based on re3data registry information	re3data	re3data	No
17	Research Performing Organisations	Organisations that perform research, and are linked to RDA activity in one way or another	Research Organisations Registry (RoR)	Research Organisations Registry (RoR)	No

18	Adoption Status	Adoption status as reflected by the RDA workflow towards outputs and supporting materials	Confirmation provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Yes
19	Technology Focus/ Research Workflow	This will be a useful addition, but it isn't clear exactly what the list should cover. Maybe include OAIS-RM?	Sample provided by DANS, confirmed by RDA	Defer to stable external source if possible, else RDA Website API	Maybe
20	Stakeholders	A curated list of the typical stakeholders in the research data management landscape	Sample provided by DANS, confirmed by RDA	Defer to stable external source if possible, else RDA Website API	Maybe
21	Language	Standardised language references	ISO 639	ISO 639-1 and 693-2	No
22	Criteria	Criteria Linked to Principles	Sample provided by DANS, confirmed by RDA	EOSC Compliance Assessment Toolkit	No
23	Global and Regional Initiatives	These are funded to provide coordination, or to provide federated infrastructure guidance or platforms to the community.	Sample provided by DANS, confirmed by RDA	Unclear	No
24	Miscellaneous Keyword Vocabularies	RDA members and experts may want to indicate and use miscellaneous vocabularies as a source of keywords	To be discussed with RDA experts	To be determined by RDA experts	No
25	DataCite Lookup Lists	For purposes of publication, DANS proposes using DataCite controlled vocabularies as metadata.	Use DataCite lookup lists for metadata fields associated with publication of not yet listed.	DataCite API	No
26	Pathways	Implementation and adoption possibilities for RDA outputs	Confirmation provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Maybe
27	(Working) Group Status	Status of groups in RDA - based on a lookup list	Confirmation provided by RDA Secretariat	RDA Website API	Maybe

28	(Working) Group Focus	One or more focus areas for working groups - possibly also interest groups	From website data	RDA Website API RDA Graph Database	Maybe
29	Managed Tag List	An open tag vocabulary that can be extended by any validated user. Includes RDA Tag Lists	Current domains and topics - see here .	RDA Website API	Maybe
30	Countries	A controlled vocabulary/ list of countries, based on ISO 3166	ISO Lists	ISO Lists as internal code list	Maybe
31	Group Workflow	A controlled vocabulary from the RDA website that is used to colour-code groups with a basic workflow state	RDA Website DB	RDA Graph database	
32	RDA Outputs		Scrape from website Zenodo	RDA Graph database	Synchronisation needed
33	Current Website Node Typology	Node classification tags or typology - used to classify web pages in the current RDA website	RDA Website DB	RDA Graph database	Not Applicable
34	Organisation Types	Organisations are classified in the RDA Website using one of these categories	RDA Website DB	RDA Website API	Maybe
35	GORC	Links to Global Open Research Commons Elements and Features. GORC Vocabulary: Elements , Attributes , Features	RDA Website for GORC WG	Vocabulary Service at ARDC	No

Table C.1 indicates which of these vocabularies and lists need to use the new RDA website as a definitive source. Engagement has started to enable this, and the [initial list of exchanges has been defined](#), together with a data model for each exchange¹⁷. Note that this list will hopefully be extended in future.

¹⁷ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1iBNPJ_Ejr3ENQWLLShQBZDU1_ykegxp_41XVMgEgMug/edit#gid=0&range=A1

Table C.2 Exchange of Vocabularies and Registry Data with RDA Website

#	Title	Description	Priority	Notes
1	Working Groups	A listing, with properties, of RDA working groups. Alternatively, an API call to list working groups, with a specific call to retrieve properties for a working group.	1. High	This call can be combined with 2, in which case the group type (working group, interest group, or any other group type) is a parameter.
2	Interest Groups	A listing, with properties, of RDA interest groups. Alternatively, an API call to list interest groups, with a specific call to retrieve properties for an interest group.	1. High	
3	Group-Group	Relation between groups - most commonly the WGs associated with an Interest Group	1. High	No <i>relationtype</i> needs to be provided, it can be inferred.
4	Members (Individuals)	A listing of RDA Members, with properties, or alternatively a call to return a listing of members with a supporting call to list details for each member	1. High	
5	Group Members	Return a list of members associated with a group, as well as the role (member, co-chair, follower)	1. High	See 'Individual_Member-Group' for details. If a member ends a role (and possibly starts another) this information can be retained in the list, so that a history of involvement can be tracked.
7	Outputs (Resources)	RDA outputs registered in the RDA website, irrespective of whether these are also present in Zenodo.	1. High	In future, RDA outputs will be published to Zenodo via the RDA-KB, and the RDA website will for the moment be updated manually by the Secretariat.
15	Resources - Individuals	A link between resources (outputs, supplementary materials, ...) and the creators of these - authors, contributors, ...	1. High	For resources published to Zenodo via the RDA-KB, this data is not needed. The relation between an individual and a resource is standardised in DataCite/ Zenodo metadata. Also note that not all authors or contributors are always RDA members - that's why we call them 'individuals'.

				Included in 'Resource' table for now.
8	Supplementary Materials (Resources)	Supplementary materials published on the RDA website, irrespective of whether these have been published in Zenodo	1. High	In future, RDA supplementary materials will be published to Zenodo via the RDA-KB, and the RDA website will for the moment be updated manually by the Secretariat.
6	BoF	Returns a list of BoF Sessions, with properties that link to members attending, the plenary where the BoF took place, and the interest groups and/ or working group(s) that were created as a result.	2. Medium	Choice of parameter to limit the size of the return data.
10	Adoption Stories	A list of adoption stories, with a property identifying the RDA output associated with it.	2. Medium	
9	Endorsements	Endorsements of group outputs by organisations (i.e. the organisations creating the adoption stories).	2. Medium	Not all endorsements have an adoption story.
11	Case Statements	Links to case statements - likely a PDF or DOC	3. Low	If the group has a predictable URL pattern for retrieving the case statement, this call is not required. URL can also be included in 'Groups'.
12	Organisations/ Institutions	These are the organisations linked to members in their biography pages - and if the website maintains a curated list, it will be really useful.	3. Low	RDA TIGER has created such a curated list that deduplicates the organisations on the basis of language, abbreviations, etc. and contains some parent-child relations. In future, using RoR to identify research organisations whenever possible is recommended.

D: Graph Database Releases

The **RDA Graph** database, after initial deployment as a Neo4J graph, was redeployed as a graph-relational database using PostGreSQL. The main motivation for this is to simplify development of applications that rely on the graph (RDA-KB, RDA Annotator, and RDA Publisher). In time, we will develop APIs to provide graph functionality to external users from the graph-relational database, and migration to a graph database in future is not excluded.

The RDA Graph Database is based on the information model in Figure D.1. The main nodes and relations in the graph are defined below:

Table D.1 Nodes and relations in the RDA Graph

1	Resource	List of resources with simple attributes
2	Resource Workflow	Relation between Resources and Workflow (Adoption state by the RDA)
3	Workflow	Workflow States (Adoption state by the RDA)
4	Resource Pathway	Relation between Resources and Pathways
5	Pathway	Pathways, overarching topics that the resources support
6	Resource-Rights	Rights afforded to users of the resource, access level and licences by the Creative Commons
7	Rights	Rights - licences and access types
8	Resource-Relation	Links to other resources - external, communities, as well as internal/self-references
9	Relation	Types of relations resources have
10	Subject-Resource	Relation between keyword terms and Resources
11	Group-Resource	Relations between Working groups, Interest Groups, and Resources
12	Individual Resource	Relation between Resources and Individuals - Authors of and Contributors to Resources
13	Individual	Individuals, including members and non-members that have contributed to or authored resources
14	Individual-Institution	Relation between individuals and institutions
15	Individual-Member	Individuals who are members of the RDA including their names and UUIDs
16	Individual-Group All	Individuals and their RDA group membership, including all members of all groups
17	Individual-Group	Overview of the co-chairs of the RDA groups
18	Institutions	Overview of institutions connected to the RDA including simple attributes

19	Institution_Country	Relation between institutions and countries
20	Institution_Organisation Type	Relation between institutions and their domains
21	Organisation_Types	Overview of overarching domains that institutions are related to
22	Institution-InstitutionRole	Relation between institution and role towards the RDA
23	Institution_Roles	Overview of roles that institutions have towards the RDA
24	WorkingGroup	RDA Working Groups including domains
25	InterestGroup	RDA Interest Groups including domains
26	Group-Group	Relation between groups, including both interest groups and working groups
27	GroupLinks	Links to groups on the RDA website
28	Additional Resources	Resources not created by the RDA or associated groups that have a relation to the RDA or groups
29	AdoptionStories	Relation between institutions and adoption stories (how institutions have adopted RDA projects)
30	Institution-Resources	Relation between institutions and resources

The RDA Graph database is now in its 3rd release, these releases are described as follows:

D.2 Release 1

Release 1 was directed at Neo4J upload, and the CSV files can be found [here](#)¹⁸.

D.2 Release 2

Starting in Release 2, the RDA Graph was converted to a set of CSV files, which could be uploaded to a graph database (such as Neo4J), but could also be uploaded to PostgreSQL - with some of the named relations converted to foreign key table relations in the RDBMS. This upload [dataset is available for the record](#)¹⁹, but should not be seen as authoritative or complete any longer.

The [data dictionary for Release 2](#)²⁰ is also available for review and download.

D.3 Release 3

Release 3 is largely a quality assurance update of Release 2, focusing on a number of aspects (deduplication of references to organisations, members, ensuring that lists of resources were up to date, looking at completeness of information on the main entities, etc.). CODATA WGs, and other relevant assets identified through the RDA TIGER Landscaping work package (WP3) were also added.

¹⁸ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1cu0f-vXjXmMNMbuvVfZF9YbgMQ23IiH?usp=drive_link

¹⁹ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1KbIFv-_bNUsSW1xAzWGpvTmnTnuSstx9?usp=drive_link

²⁰

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Iac3zgMHuKc9co-Ira1ZcWmusQ3df92YhRUjii_uErg/edit?usp=drive_link

Figure D.1 RDA Graph Information Model

Release 3 is also available in the same formats as Release 2: a set of CSV files that can be uploaded to Neo4J or to PostGreSQL, and a supporting data dictionary.

DANS expects to make 1 more release after manual updates and quality assurance, after which it is hoped that the RDA GGraph can be synchronised automatically with the new RDA website.

D: Support Documentation

D.1 Recommended RDA Resources Policy

This is due by Plenary 24 in the planning [4]. The notes below indicate the scope of the policy.

The RDA Policy should address and confirm the following:

1. The scope of applicability - who and what are impacted by the policy.
2. The roles and responsibilities of the RDA Secretariat, curators, group chairs, and systems providers in implementing RDA policy.
3. Address specific policy provisions in respect of
 - a. Licensing and intellectual property rights of RDA resources - outputs, supplementary materials, other supporting documentation.
 - b. The use of AI and ML in RDA resources.
 - c. Non-RDA members contributing to RDA resources.
 - d. Publication of RDA resources in journals and repositories other than Zenodo.
 - e. Retention and preservation of resources.
 - f. Sensitive data and privacy protection.

The policy should be structured according to the following template [6]:

Table D.1.1 Policy Structuring

#	Element	Description
1	Context and Mandate	How and why the policy came about and the authority to prescribe a policy.
2	Purpose	The objectives of writing and enforcing the policy. A goal, desirable characteristic, or outcome is described.
3	Scope and Audience	The scope of a policy needs to be defined. Most RDMI policies deal with outputs and services, and sometimes multiple types of output or services are included. Furthermore, most policies define a designated community that needs to adopt or adhere to the policy. Finally, a policy has a jurisdiction or a coverage ²¹ . The applicability of a policy is often limited with respect to a region or jurisdiction.
4	Benefits	The benefits of realising the policy. Policies often aim to improve one or more outcomes for their stakeholders.
5	Principles	The ethos behind the policy. Principles that should guide behaviour, implementation, or characteristics are described.

²¹ Spatial, domain, or both.

6	Policy Provisions	Expected performance is described - a procedural or technical aspect is often expressed. The parties responsible for realisation need to be defined. Provisions should ensure that principles are adhered to or objectives are met.
7	Oversight and Compliance	Who is responsible for the implementation and oversight of this policy?. Assessment of compliance and consequences for non-compliance are described.
8	Related Documents	Any other relevant or useful documentation.
9	Document Control	Review frequency and responsibility.
10	Glossary and Definitions	Definition of terms and concepts used in the policy.

E: Procedures

E.1 Guidance on Group Establishment

The following guidelines and best practices have been identified to date, and can be included into the recommendations for workgroup establishment. The guidelines and best practices relate to aspects to consider during the establishment phase of groups that will be useful for later management of the assets created by the group. Organisational aspects are [attended to by RDA materials](#).

Table E.1.1 - Practical Group Establishment Aspects

#	Aspect	Description
1	Collaboration Workspace Features	<p>Collaboration workspaces should be openly available, but also allow control of access as and when required. Google Drive and similar services (e.g. OneDrive, iCloud) provide these types of collaboration, with advantages and disadvantages. In short, these translate into:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. All three the mainstream services are restricted in China, and will exclude any participants from that country. There are also some restrictions in several other countries on all three - Russia, Iran, some Middle Eastern Countries, and India may also place some restrictions on use of these services. There is no mainstream service that does not face these restrictions. 2. Google Drive provides the most comprehensive features in respect of sharing and usability across platforms. OneDrive and iCloud are more suitable in Office 365 and Apple-OS environments, and some users may struggle to use them in non-Windows or non-Apple environments. 3. All these offerings have specific privacy concerns, and no one service provides a perfect solution in terms of regional or national privacy legislation. <p>If privacy is a major concern, some type of wiki-like or OwnCloud (e.g. B2DROP) may be more appropriate solutions, but these are really cumbersome to use from a sharing and collaborative editing perspective, and are not recommended.</p>
2	Collaboration Workspace Structure	<p>Consider from the start that there will be main folders organised in terms of access - at a minimum:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Content only shared with the co-chairs and promoters of the group; 2. Content only shared with group members; 3. Content available to anyone. <p>Individual objects can, of course, usually be controlled in terms of access, but it is a lot simpler to make these arrangements up front.</p>
3	Template for Group	<p>A template for establishment of a collaborative area can be obtained from the RDA TIGER project, either as an archive (ZIP file), or by copying a folder from Google Drive.</p>

E.2 Maximising Workgroup Effort

There will often be a significant investment of time, effort, and knowledge in assembling evidence, cases, and inputs in the lifetime of a group. These efforts can be mobilised and described much better so that (1) it retains context and can easily be found again by newcomers or other interested parties, and (2) it can be reused in a different context by other RDA members, groups, and initiatives.

In broad terms, the vision is to annotate these assets in such a way that they form part of the RDA Graph, findable via the Search and Discovery application, and can be referenced unambiguously by others. To do so, we request groups to take the following considerations into account.

Table E.2.1 Maximising Workgroup Efforts

#	Aspect	Description
1	FAIR Assets	The work being done by the groups in RDA often involves significant research and pooling of collective knowledge accumulated by group members over many years. Formalisation of these efforts in such a way to allow findability and reuse of especially landscape analysis results will be hugely beneficial to others. See E.3.
2	FAIR Resources	Formal outputs generated by RDA groups can be made FAIR in two ways: by ensuring that they are properly described in metadata, and by ensuring that the resources are published in designated repositories linked to the RDA Graph. See E.4
3	FAIR Recommendations	Most working groups create sets of best practices and recommendations as an output. These recommendations can be made much more useful and reusable through a process of annotation, as described in E.5.
4	Standards	Some working group outputs may qualify as standards endorsed or adopted in international standards organisations, such as IETF, W3C, or ISO. These processes are typically lengthy and resource-intensive, but RDA should nevertheless provide guidance in respect of structuring of outputs so that eventual participation in a process is simplified.

E.3 FAIR Assets: Reusable Workgroup Research

Creation of reusable working group research can be achieved in a number of ways, and the most important aspects of this relates to preparation for such reuse. This entails selection of appropriate vocabularies for contextualisation of the research, and the subsequent implementation using RDA TIGER-provided tools and infrastructure.

Table E.3.1 Making Group Research FAIR

#	Aspect	Description
1	References	Agree up front on a shared inventory of references accumulated in preparation for a BoF or the establishment of the group.

2	Annotation of References	References (web resources such as web pages, landing pages of PIDs, etc.) can be annotated - either as a specific fragment of a web resource or the resource (page) itself. By annotating these references with selected RDA vocabularies (see Annexure C), these references are added to the body of knowledge in the RDA Graph, and can be found via search and discovery in the RDA-KB. A separate guide available to end users to explain the annotation process, and how to install the RDA Annotation Tool [7].
3	Selection of Vocabularies	Each group will likely require specific vocabularies to be used for contextualisation of their research, but at present the RDA Annotation Tool only supports a set of common vocabularies ²² . The current default vocabularies are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pathways ● GORC Attributes ● GORC Elements ● Interest Groups ● Working Groups ● Domains
4	Agree on Your Own Tags (Keywords)	Each group will likely have a set of custom tags (keywords) - these can be entered as keywords and is based on a type-ahead validation of previously entered keywords. It will be good practice to agree on the set of keywords within the group and to maintain it independently for the benefit of new members of the group.

E.4 FAIR Resources: Publication and Curation of RDA Resources

RDA Resources are defined as RDA outputs, supplementary materials, and any other supporting documentation that has utility within the group or has usefulness to external users (RDA members or the general research community). Some of these resources are managed and curated to a higher standard than others, but we need to provide unified and harmonised access to these resources. To do so, the provisions in Table E.4.1 should be followed.

Table E.4.1 FAIR Publication and Curation

#	Aspect	Description		
		RDA Outputs	Supplementary Materials	Other Resources
1	Publication Target	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A journal, or 2. The RDA outputs collection in Zenodo 	The RDA supplementary collection in Zenodo	The target for publication is one of <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The RDA supplementary collection in Zenodo 2. The RDA Website 3. Any other persistent web location.

²² Extension is possible from a design perspective but not yet implemented.

2	Publication Workflow	Initiate the publication process via the RDA website. The publication workflow is described in the RDA Publication Guidance document [8].	Initiate the publication process via the RDA website.	Publish the resource using the RDA-KB (for full metadata records) or the Annotation Tool (for external, non-RDA resources).
3	Metadata	The metadata for RDA outputs need to match the schema provided in Table F.1.1.	Supplementary materials metadata also need to match the schema in Table F.1.1	Groups can choose to describe other resources using either the formal metadata schema in F.1.1, if the target is a formal collection, or the annotation schema in F.2.1 if the target is elsewhere.
4	Curation	Curation is performed by the RDA Secretariat, with assistance from RDA TIGER, on submission via the RDA website.	Curation is performed by the RDA Secretariat, with assistance from RDA TIGER, on submission via the RDA website.	The content is self-curated, with minimum annotation metadata and linked vocabularies configured in the RDA Annotation Tool.

Table E.4.2 Persistent Web Locations

#	Aspect	Description
1	Resources with Persistent Identifiers	<p>These resources have the highest probability of being resolvable for the foreseeable future. Deposits to journals, preprint servers, trustworthy repositories, and mainstream generalist repositories such as Zenodo and Figshare meet these criteria. See table E.4.3 below.</p> <p>The resources are not guaranteed to be persisted in all cases, and for that reason, the RDA RDA-KB will also mirror copies of content placed in the RDA Zenodo collections to a long-term repository.</p>
2	Public Knowledge Bases	Public Knowledge Bases (Wikipedia, WikiData, ...) have a high probability of being persistently available, but content drift and changes are not under direct control. These resources are very good for the definition of concepts and things - providing a stable URI for these.
3	RDA Website	The RDA Website should not be used as the only location for publication of content to be preserved for the long term. For content not placed in the RDA Zenodo collections, it is prudent to consider any of the options listed in Table E.4.3 in addition to the RDA Website.

Table E.4.3 Suggested Options for Resolvable Deposits

Platform	Description	Features	Identifier
Generalist Repositories			
Zenodo	A general-purpose open-access repository developed with EU funding and operated by CERN.	Accepts research outputs from all disciplines, wide variety of file types and content types.	DOI via DataCite
figshare	A repository for researchers to share their research outputs, including datasets, figures, and media.	Open access, versioning, metrics tracking, supports various file types.	DOI via DataCite
OSF (Open Science Framework)	A platform for project management and sharing research outputs, including preprints.	Integrates with various tools, supports collaboration, and open access.	DOI via CrossRef or DataCite
Dryad	A curated resource that makes the data underlying scientific publications discoverable, freely reusable, and citable.	Focuses on data associated with publications, open access.	DOI via DataCite
PLOS	A nonprofit open-access science, technology, and medicine publisher.	Peer-reviewed, open access journals, promotes open data policies.	DOI via CrossRef
Institutional Repositories	Repositories hosted by universities or research institutions to archive and provide access to their scholarly outputs.	Institution-specific, supports various types of research outputs.	Often provide DOIs or handle local identifiers
Discipline-Specific Repositories and Preprint Servers			
PubMed Central	A free archive of biomedical and life sciences journal literature.	Long-term preservation, compliance with funding agency requirements.	PMID and PMCID
arXiv	A preprint repository for physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, and statistics.	Open access, no cost for depositors, widely used in the scientific community.	arXiv ID
bioRxiv	A preprint server for biology.	Open access, dissemination of research findings.	DOI via CrossRef
medRxiv	A preprint server for health sciences.	Open access, sharing of health research.	DOI via CrossRef

E.5 FAIR Recommendations: Leveraging and Annotation

One of the objectives of the RDA TIGER project is to assist RDA groups with making their work more reusable. To achieve this, RDA TIGER will pilot procedures to annotate recommendations and best practices with those working groups that it assists.

The process of annotation is described in Annexure B, and this can be used as a basis for annotation of recommendations and best practices.

Table E.5.1 Annotating Recommendations and Best Practices

#	Aspect	Description
1	Select Vocabularies	The appropriate vocabularies for annotating and contextualising recommendations and best practices must be selected and agreed by the group, with the aim of maximising reuse.
2	Mandatory Vocabularies	We suggest that the following vocabularies be considered mandatory for annotating best practices and recommendations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pathways ● GORC Attributes ● GORC Elements ● Domains In addition, the interest group and/ or working group that has developed the recommendations need to be included.

E.6 Creation of Standards

This aspect has not yet been developed by WP4, but contact has been initiated with [HSBooster](#), an EU-funded project that aims to improve the creation of formal standards from EU-funded projects and initiatives.

It is unlikely that RDA groups will be able to pursue the actual standardisation process within the typical scope of an RDA group, but the intention is to ensure that aspects (nature and scope of information, other design considerations) required for the standardisation process are visible and are taken into account by RDA groups.

F: Metadata Schema

F.1 Resource Metadata

This schema is applicable to deposits that are made to Zenodo (mostly RDA outputs and supplementary materials).

Table F.1.1 Deposit Metadata Schema (Resources and Supporting Materials)

Source	Category	Element	Description	Obligation	Vocabulary Source(s)/ definition
DataCite	Administrative	Identifier	Assigned by the system based on Zenodo, has to be unique by deposit	Mandatory	Zenodo allocates a PID
Datacite, Zenodo	Administrative	Depositor	Information about the depositor - can be an account identifier	Mandatory	
Zenodo	Administrative	Created	Creation time of deposition	Mandatory	
Zenodo	Administrative	Modified	Last modified date	Optional	
DataCite	Administrative	Available	In case of an embargo the embargo date, else publication date	Recommended	
DataCite	Administrative	UploadState	The state of the deposit	Mandatory	In progress, done, error
DataCite	Administrative	PublicationState	The state of the deposit	Mandatory	submitted, published
DataCite	Administrative	PublicationState	The state of the deposit	Mandatory	submitted, published
Zenodo	Administrative	Files	A list of deposition files resources	Mandatory	
Zenodo	Administrative	Files	A list of deposition files resources	Mandatory	
DataCite	Administrative	Language	Language of the deposited resource(s)	Recommended	Language List

Zenodo	Administrative	Metadata	Original metadata	Optional	
DataCite, Zenodo	Citation	Title	A title provided by the depositor	Mandatory	
DataCite	Citation	Subtitle	A subtitle provided by the depositor	Optional	
DataCite, Zenodo	Citation	Contributors	Name of authors and contributors, as well as a PID (e.g. ORCID)	Mandatory	ORCID
DataCite, Zenodo	Citation	ContributionType	The type of contribution made by individuals	Mandatory	Zenodo contributor types
DataCite, Zenodo	Citation	Description	Some context on the deposit. Guidelines to be provided by RDA.	Mandatory	
DataCite	Citation	Publisher	Institution - often the rights holder	Mandatory	RoR Registry
DataCite, Zenodo	Citation	Publication Date	The date of publication of the resource	Mandatory	
DataCite	Coverage	Location (Geolocation)	The location(s) that the material deals with	Recommended	Geonames
DataCite	Coverage	Data Time and Date	The start and end times that the interview deals with	Recommended	
DataCite	Coverage	Keywords	Selected from a predefined list applicable to RDA activities and resources	Mandatory	Multiple Vocabularies
RDA Schema	Coverage	Keywords - Domain	RDA-Specific Keywords	Mandatory	Domain Vocabulary
RDA Schema	RDA-Specific	Keywords - Origin	A working group, interest group, other group or BoF in RDA	Mandatory	RDA Groups
RDA Schema	RDA-Specific	Keywords - Pathways	RDA Pathway classification	Recommended	Pathway vocabulary
RDA Schema	RDA-Specific	Keywords - GORC	Links to Global Open Research Commons Elements and Features	Recommended	GORC Vocabulary: Elements , Attributes , Features

DataCite	Relations	Related to	Other PIDs, publications, projects	Recommended	Relations Vocabulary
DataCite	Rights, Licencing and Reuse	Rightsholder	Name of the organisation or individual(s) owning the work	Mandatory	RoR Registry , ORCID
Zenodo	Rights, Licencing and Reuse	AccessType	The type of access provided to the resource	Mandatory	Zenodo Access Types
DataCite, Zenodo	Rights, Licencing and Reuse	Licence	One of a number of specific licences	Mandatory	Licence Registry
Zenodo	Rights, Licencing and Reuse	UploadType	Type of uploaded content	Mandatory	Zenodo Upload Types
Zenodo	Rights, Licencing and Reuse	PublicationType	If the upload type is a publication, a subtype must be specified	Conditional	Zenodo Publication Types
Zenodo	Rights, Licencing and Reuse	ImageType	If the upload type is media or images, a subtype must be specified	Conditional	Zenodo Image Types

F.2 Annotation Metadata

This schema is applicable to annotation of web resources.

Table F.2.1 Annotation Schema

Source	Category	Element	Description	Obligation	Vocabulary Source(s)/ definition
System	Administrative	Identifier	Assigned by the system system	Mandatory	
System	Administrative	Depositor	Information about the annotator - can be an account identifier	Mandatory	
System	Administrative	Created	Creation time of annotation	Mandatory	
System	Administrative	Language	Language of the annotated resource	Recommended	Language List

Web Resource	Administrative	Fragment	Web URL or PID, with or without fragment definition	Mandatory	
System	Citation	Title	A title provided by the annotator	Mandatory	
System	Citation	Notes	Additional information	Optional	
System	Citation	Description	Some context on the annotation. Guidelines to be provided by RDA.	Mandatory	
System	RDA-Specific	Keywords - Domain	RDA-Specific Keywords	Mandatory	Domain Vocabulary
System	RDA-Specific	Keywords - Origin	A working group, interest group, other group or BoF in RDA	Mandatory	RDA Groups
System	RDA-Specific	Keywords - Pathways	RDA Pathway classification	Recommended	Pathway vocabulary
System	RDA-Specific	Keywords - GORC	Links to Global Open Research Commons Elements and Features	Recommended	GORC Vocabulary: Elements , Attributes , Features
System	Relations	Related to	Other PIDs, publications, projects	Recommended	Relations Vocabulary

G: Preferred Formats - Guidance and Tools

The draft preferred formats guidance is based on content developed by DANS, which in turn is the result of a continuous monitoring and engagement effort by the DANS Data Curators.

Preferred formats are those of which one is confident that they will offer the best **long-term** guarantees in terms of usability, accessibility and sustainability.

Format guidance has two separate objectives, and these do not always result in the same format recommendations:

1. For dissemination, current popular formats are often preferred, although these may not be optimally preservable.
2. For preservation, the main consideration is whether such formats will be human- and machine-readable in the long term in the absence of specific software.

In practice, it is not always possible to use formats which satisfy all of these criteria.

Table G.1 Preferred Formats

Type	Long-Term Preservation	Dissemination	Recommendation
Documents	PDF/A (.pdf) ODT (.odt)	Microsoft Word (.doc) Office Open XML (.docx) Rich Text File (.rtf) PDF other than PDF/A (.pdf)	PDF/A (.pdf)
Plain text	Unicode text (.txt)	Non-Unicode text (.txt)	Unicode text (.txt)
Markup language	XML (.xml) HTML (.html) Related files: .css , .xslt , .js , .es	SGML (.sgml) Markdown (.md)	Any Unicode text file
Spreadsheets	ODS (.ods) CSV (.csv)	Microsoft Excel (.xls) Office Open XML Workbook (.xlsx) PDF/A (.pdf)	CSV (.csv) If CSV will result in loss of formula logic, use .xlsx

Databases	SQL (.sql) SIARD (.siard) CSV (.csv)	Microsoft Access (.mdb, .accdb) dBase (.dbf) HDF5 (.hdf5, .he5, .h5)	SQL (.sql) Export the SQL statements required to create and update all tables and views
Statistical data	SPSS (.dat/.sps) STATA (.dat/.DO) JASP (.csv/.html) R	SPSS Portable (.por) SPSS (.sav) STATA (.dta) SAS (.7dat; .sd2; .tpt) JASP (.jasp)	SPSS (.dat/.sps) STATA (.dat/.DO) JASP (.csv/.html) R
Raster images	JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg) TIFF (.tif, .tiff) PNG (.png) JPEG 2000 (.jp2) DICOM (.dcm)		JPEG (.jpg, .jpeg) TIFF (.tif, .tiff) PNG (.png) JPEG 2000 (.jp2) DICOM (.dcm)
Vector images	SVG (.svg)	Adobe Illustrator (.ai) EPS (.eps) WMF/EMF (.wmf, .emf) CDR (.cdr)	SVG (.svg)
Audio	BWF (.bwf) MXF (.mxf) Matroska (.mka) FLAC (.flac) OPUS	WAVE (.wav) MP3 (.mp3) AAC (.aac, .m4a) AIFF (.aif, .aiff) OGG (.ogg)	Matroska (.mka) Or MP3 (.mp3)
Video	MXF (.mxf) Matroska (.mkv)	MPEG-4 (.mp4, .m4a, .m4v, ...) MPEG-2 (.mpg, .mpeg, .m2v, .mpg2, ...) AVI (.avi) QuickTime (.mov, .qt)	Matroska (.mkv) Or MPEG-4 (.mp4)
3D	WaveFront Object (.obj) Polygon file format (.ply) X3D (.x3d) COLLADA (.dae)	Autodesk FBX (.fbx) Blender (.blend) 3D PDF (.pdf)	WaveFront Object (.obj)
RDF	RDF/XML (.rdf) Trig (.trig) Turtle (.ttl) NTriples (.nt)		RDF/XML (.rdf) Trig (.trig) Turtle (.ttl) NTriples (.nt)

	JSON-LD		JSON-LD
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If you encounter any formats that are not listed, submit a ticket via the HelpDesk or contact the TIGER support team.

H: Continuous Improvement

H.1 Helpdesk Implementation

The helpdesk implementation is based on a mainstream licensed helpdesk and user support service that is cloud-based, and can be accessed through multiple channels.

The preferred channel is via a floating support button that is always visible in deployments of the RDA-KB and the Annotation Tool (see Figure H.1.1).

Figure H.1.1 Invoking the Support Form to Post an Issue, Comment, or Request for Assistance

The ticket system supports the progress of a ticket through a workflow, as defined in Table H.1.1.

Table H.1.1: Ticket Workflow States

#	Internal State	Description
3	Open	The default state of a ticket that has not been responded to yet and for which the next step (usually 'In Process') has not been activated.
2	Responded	This shows the system that we have responded to the requester. The response time is tracked by the service level agreement applicable to the product. Sometimes a ticket can be closed after this first response. It is not the same as a receipt for the ticket, which the requester receives automatically.
4	Resolved-Linked	Some tickets can be resolved by linking them to existing tickets. It must still be verified by the agent. It may be a duplicate of the same problem, but it isn't always - in some cases related tickets are due to the same root cause but are experienced in more than one way.
5	Pending	A ticket has been put on hold for future attention. Useful for low priority tickets.
6	Waiting on User	Progress depends on information or feedback from the requester.
7	Waiting on Third Party	Progress depends on information or feedback from someone outside DANS, other than the requester
8	In Process	The default state when we are working on resolving a ticket.
9	Testing	DANS must test the solution once a it has been found or proposed. Default next state is 'Resolved'. Often, the agent will be responsible for testing. This confirms internally that the solution is valid.
10	Resolved	The agent must confirm with the requester that the solution works.
11	Closed	Agent closes the ticket once the requester has confirmed resolution.

Users can post suggestions, issues, and questions about application use via the helpdesk, and the processing of these requests are handled via the DANS support staff mechanism. The mechanism has the following characteristics:

1. Users receive an immediate automated acknowledgement via email.
2. Tickets are processed within the guardrails of an SLA (See H.2). The response time and allowable resolution time are determined by the priority of the ticket.
3. An agent is assigned to the ticket. The agent is responsible for ensuring that the ticket is resolved within the limits of the SLA, irrespective of who contributes to its resolution.
4. Some suggestions for improvement will not be accommodated due to lack of common benefit, lack of resources to implement, or other related factors. The decision not to implement a suggested improvement will also be accommodated. These suggestions are not discarded, but placed on a backlog ('Pending') for future re-evaluation.

H.2 Service Level Agreement

Table H.2 Service Level Agreement

Issue Priority	Description	Response Guidance	Resolution Guidance
Critical/ Showstopper	The user or institution is unable to use the system, or the system is unavailable	Immediate in working hours, else next working day	As soon as possible 4 hours guideline for first communication of progress
High	The functionality of the system is impaired significantly but users have a workaround, or can defer the functionality (Documented use cases and tests)	Same working day	Reasonable time, communicated in initial response. Matter of days if feasible - 5 working days
Low	The system functions as advertised but is not satisfactory for one of a number of generic reasons (user friendliness and experience, response, ...)	Same working day	No commitment required. Could be deferred indefinitely if not a common problem

H.3 Alternative Channels and Tracking Issues

Users can also submit tickets via email to the support address (ict-support@dans.knaw.nl), but this is discouraged for normal use. The email tickets are registered in the ticket system and follow the same workflow from there onwards.

Users can track issues via the DANS Ticket System portal (<https://dans.freshdesk.com/>), and also submit tickets via the portal.

H.4 Access to Guidance, Procedures, and Support Documentation

TBC

J: RDA Community Governance - Permanent Working Group

A permanent working group should be promoted within RDA to address the following aspects of RDA asset management:

1. Agreeing and maintaining RDA Vocabularies.
2. Maintenance and improvement/ extension of curation and asset management procedures
3. Management of user feedback on RDA infrastructure developed by RDA TIGER (RDA-KB, Annotation Tool, and supporting software components).
4. Contributions to the open source development of the components in collaboration with other users in the EU and globally.
5. Curation of and maintenance of the RDA Graph.

A BoF session is planned for RDA Plenary 23 to initiate creation of such a working group.

K: New naming scheme since fall 2024

Table K.1: Overview of naming changes

Old name	New name	Brief description
Maintenance Platform / Maintenance Facility	RDA Knowledge Base	The system as a whole, consisting of the components below. Demo version currently hosted by DANS ²³
Graph Database / RDA Graph	RDA Graph	The graph database containing information about outputs, authors, groups and their relationships
Deposit Pipeline	RDA Publisher	The common update path of the RDA Graph supporting automatic addition of relationships and sanity checking of entries
The Web Interface	RDA Discovery	Query the RDA Graph, search outputs, and add entries through a web interface
Annotation tool	RDA Annotator	A browser plugin allowing adding entries (through the RDA Publisher) and “tagging them” using RDA vocabularies

²³ <https://rda.dansdemo.nl>

Figure K.1: RDA Applications in the RDA Knowledge Base suite, and its relation to e.g. Zenodo²⁴

²⁴ Adopted from the WP4 presentation at the RDA P23, available at:
https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1D7Swi_G_Uyu6TTRW0QRtwtddbboSOAxpjOffdEmhZJnk/edit#slide=id.g31257ed873b_0_263

